

FEAR IN CHILDREN AND PSYCHOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF ITS ELIMINATION

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Annotation: Children can face fears at different ages. One of the tasks of psychology is to teach to overcome this fear and prevent it. This article is devoted to the discussion of such issues.

Keywords: anxiety, fear, biological level fear, instinct, absorbed fear, reflex, threat, negative attitude.

INTRODUCTION

The reforms carried out today in the educational process are aimed at bringing the young and harmoniously developed generation to a mentally, morally and spiritually healthy development and instilling in them personal qualities.

The problem of fears in children is relevant, since excessively expressed fears can lead to developmental disorders. It is generally accepted that fear is present in all people, but manifests itself differently depending on age, gender, specific life situation, etc. It is believed that fear is directly related to the instinct of self-preservation. Special importance is attached to fears, where the so-called starting point can be identified, for example, being in a war zone, a serious illness, an animal bite and other psycho-traumatic events.

Fear of something is typical for children. It is important not to be indifferent to children's fears, but to fight them. In such cases, it is necessary to build a trusting relationship between adults and children. In some cases, we see children with stuttering, nocturnal and daytime enuresis, headaches, anxiety, and various somatic symptoms. These diseases and conditions are based on childhood fears [1].

Fear prevents a person from enjoying life. This may manifest itself in the following way.

1. Fear at the biological level is characterized by the release of a large amount of adrenaline into the blood, which causes a hormonal explosion in the human body.
2. Psychological fear is the fear of situations (objects, people, events), which is determined by the release of the same hormone.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The features of the social development of a preschooler are reflected in specific activities for him, especially in games and fairy tales.

Fear is an unpleasant feeling in our daily life that we experience several times a day and become addicted.

When we first experience the biological effects of fear in childhood, we experience fear again later in life in similar situations. It is difficult to find a person who is not afraid of anything. Worry, anxiety and fear are also integral aspects of our psychological life, such as joy, pride, anger and amazement. However, as a result of excessive involvement with fear, people's behavior can change to the point of "emotional paralysis."

Constant fear is a condition that neither adults nor children can overcome, which leads to some negative personality traits.

There are two opposite opinions about the functional significance of fears in children and adolescents, depending on the functionality/dysfunctionality of the family, on the specifics of coping behavior, on the fixation of children's anxieties that set the vector of normal or impaired mental development. The first is that the child's fear shows an adult his vulnerability, vulnerability, increased anxiety and, as a result, parents and other adults should further protect the child from life's difficulties and possible dangers, thereby protecting the child's nervous system. Another opinion is that fear is a manifestation of weakness, a decrease in volitional qualities, cowardice, and this must be overcome even in childhood; one should not follow the child's lead, otherwise an unsuccessful, so-called neurotic personality will grow up [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are vulnerabilities in both approaches. The strategy of working with a child in the first variant can lead to a limitation of the child's independence, increased guardianship on the part of parents, as a result of which the child is even more isolated from the outside world, and his anxieties and fears only intensify, in particular due to anxiety. and suspiciousness of close adults. In the second option, when children do not find emotional support in the family, they stop turning to their relatives for help with their experiences. And here there is a serious danger in the deformation of the child's personality, his emotional disturbances in the form of increased rigidity, selfishness. Nevertheless, such a harsh way of getting rid of fears can determine the situational result for parents and teachers, but usually entails serious difficulties for the child himself in the future: inability to show his feelings, unformed feelings of attachment to someone, duality in character, etc., which prevents personal communication with friends and members of the future own family.

The most optimal attitude to fears in children and adolescents is quite calm, balanced: without expressed anxiety and anxiety or condemnation, and even more punishment. If the degree of manifestation of fear is not high and is episodic, then it is necessary to distract the child from these fears: go on a picnic together, ride with the whole family on sleds, rollerblades, skates, bicycles, do some interesting activity - folding pictures from puzzles, constructing something, gluing models of cars, ships, etc. The child must be occupied so that he does not have time to fix on fears. He must also be sure of the support and love of his relatives, who, if necessary, will protect him. Usually children "outgrow" fears, that is, they themselves disappear or become irrelevant. This is facilitated by the intellectual comprehension of fears in older children, which also reduces their negative impact.

When the child gets older, he or she will begin to explore the world under the guidance of adults. The physical and psychological well-being of a child depends on our words and actions. It is important to remember that verbal negligence, excessive caution, or unreasonable threats can cause fear or anxiety in a child. We try to change

everything when we teach children to be afraid, and then when it becomes a disease, it will be difficult to do so. The program mastered by childhood is strong.

The well-known physiologist I. P. Pavlov considered fear to be a passive defensive reaction, a manifestation of a natural reflex, accompanied by a slight depression of the cerebral cortex. Fear is based on the instinct of self-defense, is protective in nature and is associated with certain changes in higher nervous activity - a pulse and respiratory rate appear, blood pressure readings, secretion of gastric juice.

The most common fear is the fear that is instilled in children. The source of this is the adults around the children who, out of ignorance, inspire fear in the children, that is, they are too strict and emotionally dangerous. As a result, children understand and receive only 2 parts of speech, such as “do not come close - you will fall”, “do not touch - you will burn yourself”, “do not caress - he will bite”. The child naturally develops a fearful reaction, even if he does not realize what the danger may be. This will increase the fear. Anxious parents can also influence external fears. With children, they talk about topics that affect his psyche and weaken him, like death, illness, murder. When a child is suddenly frightened by a knock, and this causes him discomfort, all this forms the basis of the conditioned reflex nature of fear. This state is stored in the memory of the child and is repeated the next time under the influence of any random sounds.

Fears are associated with age, and over time, these fears will be overcome. But in emotional children, these fears can take root. The most fearless period is 3 years for girls and 4 years for boys. As children get older, their fears intensify. Children from dysfunctional families are more afraid. Especially for boys who live alone with their mothers. This is because the child grows up without seeing in the example a person (father) of the same sex, and self-confidence, self-esteem becomes passive.

Exercise "Find the figure."

Purpose: to show that, demonstrating the illusion of perception, a person cannot always correctly perceive the situation, that various unpleasant experiences

arise not because of the situation, but because of the person's reaction to this situation [2].

Participants will be shown various forms. We ask them how he perceives these forms. This exercise is based on the perceptual illusion that one image is perceived differently than another.

Everything you see in life is not always true!!! Psychologist: A person cannot always understand the situation correctly. To avoid this situation, it is necessary to study the situation from all sides, to learn to see the other side of the image. The choice of what to do should be left to the child: draw, tell a story, tell a story, or act in a play. This is a great way to deal with the internal problems of the child. However, it should be borne in mind that the treatment of children without the influence of parents does not give positive results. The joint work of a psychologist with the child's family is the first step towards the well-being of the future generation.

CONCLUSION

The reaction of parents to fear should be calm and understandable. This is not something to be taken lightly or overly worried about. Talk to your child about his fears and ask him to describe what he is afraid of. The more the child talks about fear, the better the treatment will be for him. The more the child talks, the less he is afraid. You can come up with a story or activity to overcome your fears. The methods of overcoming children's fears in psychotherapy include the following [3].

1. Paint a picture of fear. - A neurotic child should depict his fear on a piece of paper. This task is done at home for 2 weeks. In the next lesson, the child is asked to draw on a piece of paper how he is not afraid of the same fear. In this way, unconscious fear is raised to the level of consciousness, and the child thinks about his fear and gets rid of it. There were cases when children refused to draw on the back of paper. They said they were afraid and didn't know what to do.

In such cases, the psychologist can take a piece of paper with a picture of the child's fear, burn it, and tell the child, "You see, there is only a little ash left of the creature you fear. Now we have blown it and the fear is gone." It's a bit of a myth, but it does work.

2. Write a story on the topic of fear - In this case, the psychologist's task is to bring the child closer to real life, to teach him to understand that his fear is imaginary. This is achieved by adding elements of humor to the story. Such stories can be created on topics that the child likes.

3. Use a variety of games, shows and scenes. In group activities, children are asked to compose a scary tale or story. This story may start with "The veins were...", "Once upon a time...". Fairy tales of children with anxiety neurosis usually end sadly. Children should be able to act out fairy tales or stories of their choice. In this case, the distribution of roles is made by the author of the fairy tale. It would be advisable if these scenes are small and take the form of a dialogue. One character is positive and the other is negative.

4. Use of scary movies. - Although this method is controversial, but its use is effective. The premise is that the film should be about that fear. For example, fear of earthquakes, natural disasters, etc.

5. Imagination. - Fear is not expressed in all children. There are times when a child develops unexplained anxiety and depression. In such cases, neurotic children are asked to close their eyes and meditate on "How I represent my fears." When the child fantasizes about his fears, he should be encouraged to speak on behalf of the fear, and changes in the intonation of the child's speech should be observed in the process of expressing the imaginary event or image.

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